

ORGANIZATIONAL WORK ENVIRONMENT AND ITS EFFECTS ON EXXONMOBIL EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN EKET, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This research examines the effects of organizational work environment of ExxonMobil in relation to its employee's performance with specific attention to work condition, work culture and physical work environment. To achieve this, descriptive research survey design was used; population of study covered only 270 permanent staff of Exxon Mobil Corporation, Eket drawn from selected departments - Finance department, Human resource management department, Safety department, Security department, and Operational department. Adopting ratio sampling technique, the researcher selected 2/3 of the total population of the study. In effect, the sample size of the study covered 180 employees from the selected departments. Primary data used in the study were got from the administration/retrieval of structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage and mean analysis were used to analyze the data collected, while multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The result revealed, among others, that 70.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that terms of employment (contract / permanent staff, benefits and pay time) increases employee performance in ExxonMobil, Eket. From the tested

hypotheses, the empirical result also revealed that work condition and work environment in ExxonMobil have significant effects on employee performance. It is therefore, recommended that ExxonMobil Corporation, Eket must maintain a better environment in order to enhance employee productivity as employee performance and workplace environment have direct and positive relationship.

Keywords: Exxon Mobil, Work Condition, employee's performance

Introduction

In a typical working environment, significant components are physical and behavioural constituents. Elements which are associated with employee's physical attachment and the office environment are referred to as physical environment. Office environment influences the behaviours of individual employees. Thus, the excellence of working environment act as an essential function in determining the level of employees' and workers' motivation, productivity and performance.

Healthy and safe working environment can take a very central role in increasing productivity. Unfortunately, most of the employers consider it as an extra cost and do not spend much on maintaining comfortable working environment. Looking at a group of people working at the same time, one would observe that some people do it better than others while some are uninterested. This behaviour raises some questions and doubts by the observer as to why some people like to work while others are unwilling to do so? The reasons for this action border on employee's work environment.

The environment can be a substantive issue which concerns actual terms and environment such as pay, holidays and fringe benefits, etc. This will also cover such items as environmental factors relevant to efficiency or enjoyment of job like safety, health and welfare of the employees. A group of psychologists has stressed the importance of good working environment on the wellbeing of the employees. Bad working environment affects the morale of employees and tends to have a negative impact on their willingness to work. A great deal of work has been linking the working environment of a particular work to physical and mental health. It has also been known that poor mental health was directly related to unpleasant working environment. It is therefore good to have a good working environment in order to maintain a healthy mental state and increase organizational performance.

Work environment, according to Nuraini (2013), is everything around the employees which affect performance in an assigned task, for example, the availability of the air conditioner (AC), adequate lighting, etc. To design a work environment, there are two things to note - the physical environment and social environment in the workplace. The work environment is good or applicable if people can perform activities optimally, safely, and comfortably.

ExxonMobil Corporation has good performance when it comes to providing a standard environment for work. The workplace environment impacts employee's morale, productivity and engagement - both positively and negatively. The work place environment in a majority of industry is unsafe and unhealthy; these include poorly designed workstations, unsuitable furniture, lack of ventilation, inappropriate lighting, excessive noise, insufficient safety measures in fire emergencies and lack of personal protective equipment. People working in such environment are prone to occupational disease and it impacts on employee's performance. Thus, productivity is decreased. It is the quality of the employee's workplace environment that mostly impacts on their level of motivation and subsequent performance. How well they engage with the organization, especially with their immediate environment, influences (to a great extent) their error rate, level of innovation and collaboration with other employees, absenteeism and ultimately, how long they stay in the job. Creating a work environment in which employees are productive is essential in profit making for organizations, corporations, or small businesses.

The management that dictates exactly how to maximize employee productivity center around two major areas of focus: personal motivation, and the infrastructure of the work environment. The organization would provide their employees a pleasant working environment so that the employees can concentrate on their task and became more productive.

Statement of Problem

Work environment is a vital element of an organization that has been given less consideration by businesses and companies' proprietors. Employees work in insecure and unhealthy environment which affects the overall productivity of the organization (Chandrasekar, 2011). Most organizations across the world ignore building wholesome work environments but expect maximum performance from employees. Even with no payment of salaries, no health benefits, and the environment they are working in is not conducive or safe enough; this is the dilemma workers in several organizations have to endure. Several industries do not have a

good work environment; employees are maltreated in various ways, including work place bullying, work place politics, bureaucracy, etc. Employees are facing grave environmental troubles in their related workplaces, especially in the software industry, where there are difficulties in supplying essential amenities to ameliorate their level of performance. Predicated on the above, this paper therefore, seeks to evaluate how work environment affects the performance of the employees using Exxon Mobil as a case study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the influence of organizational work environment on performance of employees in ExxonMobil, Eket, Akwa Ibom State. However, the specific objectives were to:

- i. Determine how work condition in ExxonMobil Eket affects employee performance;
- ii. Determine how the work culture in ExxonMobil Eket affects employee performance;
- iii. Determine how physical environment ExxonMobil Eket affects employee performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. How does work condition in ExxonMobil affect employee performance?
- ii. How does work culture in ExxonMobil affect employee performance?
- iii. How does physical environment in ExxonMobil affect employees' performance?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were stated in their null form were tested:

- H0₁**: work condition in ExxonMobil has no significant effect on employee performance.
- H0₂**: work culture in ExxonMobil has no significant effect on employee performance.
- H0₃**: physical work environment in ExxonMobil has no significant effect on employee performance.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Overview of Organizational Work Environment on Employee Performance.

There are many organizations in which employees encounter working conditions problems related to environmental and physical factors. A research indicates that improving the working environment reduces complaints and absenteeism while increasing productivity (Roelofsen, 2002).

In recent years, employees' comfort on the job, determined by workplace conditions and environment, has been recognized as an important factor for measuring their productivity. This is particularly true for those employees who spend most of the day operating a computer terminal. As more and more computers are being installed in workplaces, an increasing number of businesses have been adopting ergonomic designs for offices and plant installations. Ergonomics, also called biomechanics, has become popular because of demand of workers for more human comfort.

A widely accepted assumption is that better workplace environment motivates employees and produces better results. Office environment can be described in terms of physical and behavioural components. These components can further be divided in the form of different independent variables. An organization's physical environment and its design and layout can affect employee behaviour in the workplace. Brill (1992) estimates that improvements in the physical design of the workplace may result in a 5-10 percent increase in employee productivity. Consequently, the physical environment is a tool that can be leveraged both to improve business results and employee well-being (Huang, Robertson and Chang, 2004).

Ensuring adequate facilities are provided to employees is critical to generating greater employee commitment and productivity. The provision of inadequate equipment and adverse working conditions has been shown to affect employee commitment and intention to stay with the organization.

The indoor environment has the biggest effect on productivity in relation to job stress and job dissatisfaction. As suggested by Govindarajulu (2004), in the twenty-first century, businesses are taking a more strategic approach to environmental management to enhance their productivity through improving the performance level of the employees. It is evident that the more satisfied workers are with their jobs, the better the company is likely to perform well in terms of subsequent profitability and particularly productivity.

Haynes (2008) explains the behavioural office environment. Behavioral components of the office environment have the greatest impact on office productivity. In all of the work patterns, it was found that interaction was perceived to be the component to have the most positive effect on productivity, and distraction was perceived to have the most negative. Also, Patterson et al. (1997) added that people are the most valuable resource of an organization, and that the management of people makes a difference to company performance.

An attractive and supportive work environment can be described as an environment that attracts individuals into the health professions, encourages them to remain in the health workforce and enables them to perform effectively (Harvard Business Review 2015). The purpose of providing attractive work environments is to create incentives for entering the health professions (recruitment) and for remaining in the health workforce (retention). Working environment can be divided into two components namely physical and behavioural components (routledge.com). The physical environment consists of elements that relate to the office occupiers' ability to physically connect with their office environment. The behavioural environment consists of components that relate to how well the office occupiers connect with each other, and the impact the office environment can have on the behaviour of the individual.

According to Haynes (2008), the physical environment with the productivity of its occupants falls into two main categories office layout (open plan versus cellular offices) and office comfort (matching the office environment to the work processes), and the behavioural environment represents the two main components namely interaction and distraction.

The empirical research by Stall has also showed that when human needs are considered in office design, employees work more efficiently. Strong et al. (1999) also observed that social, organizational and physical context serve as the impetus for tasks and activities, and considerably influence workers' performance.

Fig 2.1 Operational Framework

Physical Work Environment

Physical work environment can determine if a person is fit or misfit to the environment of the workplace. It is also known as an ergonomic workplace. According to Amir (2010), physical workplace is an area in an organization that is being arranged so that the goal of the organization could be achieved. Researches on the workplace environment need to be done in order to get an ergonomic workplace for each of the employees. Result of the employees' performance can be increased from five to ten percent depending on the improvement of the physical workplace design (Brill, 1992). According to Amir (2010), elements that relate to the working environment include the office layout plan and the office comfort.

Company Culture

Company culture can be defined as a set of shared values, goals, attitudes and practices that characterize an organization. It's the way people feel about the work they do, the values they believe in, where they see the company going, and what they are doing to get there. The key to a successful organization is to have a culture based on a strongly held and widely shared set of beliefs that are supported by strategy and structure. When an organization has strong culture, three things happen: employees know how top management wants them to respond to any situation, employees believe that the expected response is the proper one, and employees know that they will be rewarded for demonstrating the organization's value.

Employee Performance

Sinha (2001) stated that employees' performance is depending on the willingness and also the openness of the employees itself on doing their job. He also stated that by having this willingness and openness of the employees in doing their job, it could increase the employees' productivity which also leads to good performance. A reward system should be implemented based on the performance of the employees. This is to motivate the employees in order to perform more on their task. There are several factors described by Stup (2003) towards the success of the employees' performance. The factors include physical work environment, equipment, meaningful work, performance expectation, and feedback on performance, reward for good or bad system, standard operating procedures, knowledge, skills and attitudes. Franco et al. (2002) defined performance that relies on internal motivation but presence of internal factors such as necessary skills, intellectual capacity and resources to do the job clearly have an impact. As a consequence, employers are supposed to provide appropriate working conditions in order to make sure the performance of employees meet the required standards.

Fig 2.1 Operational Framework

The framework above explains the relationship / association between organizational work environment and employee performance.

Theoretical Framework

This research is anchored on some relevant theories, one of which was proposed by

Edwin Locke (1968). Locke's goal-setting theory suggests that the individual goals established by an employee play an important role in motivating him for superior performance. Skills required include the ability to engage employees in mutual goal setting; time and energy will also need to be given to provide relevant performance incentives, managing processes, providing adequate resources and workplace training. Employees 'goals achievement' in this theory is by making work environment attractive, comfortable, satisfactory and motivating to employees so as to give them a sense of pride and purpose in what they do.

Expectancy theory as propounded by Victor Vroom also gives a wide accepted explanation of motivation. The theory argues that the strength of a tendency to act in a specific way depends on the strength of an expectation that the act will be followed by a given outcome, and on the attractiveness of that outcome to the individual to make this simple. Expectancy theory says that an employee can be motivated to perform better when there is a belief that the better performance will lead to good performance appraisal and shall result in realization of personal goal in form of some rewards. The theory focuses on three things - efforts and performance relationship; performance and reward relationship; rewards and personal goal relationship (Salaman et al., 2005). This theory is based on the hypothesis that individuals adjust their behaviour in the organization on the basis of anticipated satisfaction of valued goals set by them. To adopt this theory, employers should make sure each employee's workplace goals and values are aligned with the organization's mission and vision.

Abraham Maslow's hierarchy theory sees need as a physiological or psychological deficiency that a person feels the compulsion to satisfy. This need can create tensions that can influence a person's work attitudes and behaviours. Maslow formed this theory based on his definition of need that proposes that humans are motivated by multiple needs and that these needs exist in a hierarchical order. His premise is that only unsatisfied need can influence behaviour; a satisfied need is not a motivator (Ramlall, 2004). A person starts at the bottom of the hierarchy (pyramid) and will initially seek to satisfy basic needs (e.g., food, shelter). Once these physiological needs have been satisfied, they are no longer motivators. The individual moves up to the next level.

Esteem needs are about being given recognition for a job well done. They reflect the fact that many people seek the esteem and respect of others, and a promotion at work might achieve this.

Herzberg's theory concludes that certain factors in the workplace result in job satisfaction, but if absent, they do not lead to dissatisfaction but no satisfaction. The factors that motivate people can change over their lifetime, but "respect for me as a person" is one of the top motivating factors at any stage of life. He distinguished between motivators (e.g., challenging work, recognition, responsibility) which give positive satisfaction, and hygiene factors (e.g., status, job security, salary and fringe benefits) that do not motivate if present; but, if absent, result in demonization. The theory is sometimes called the "Motivator-Hygiene Theory" and/or "The Dual Structure Theory." Herzberg described four basic states that could occur:

1. High Motivation/High Hygiene: Perfect state of happy, motivated employees
2. High Motivation/Low Hygiene: Motivated employees who love the work but have lots of Complaints
3. Low Motivation/High Hygiene: Bored employees punching a clock for a Pay check
4. Low Motivation/Low Hygiene: Total mess of bored, unhappy employees.

Herzberg's research proved that people will strive to achieve 'hygiene' needs because they are unhappy without them; but once satisfied, the effect soon wears off as satisfaction is temporary.

Research Methodology/Design

The researchers used descriptive research survey design in building up this work. The choice of this method was considered appropriate because of its advantages of identifying attributes of a large population from a group of individuals. The design was suitable for the study as the study sought to examine the effect of organizational work environment on employees' performance. Primary data include the information and facts obtained from questionnaires issued and interview of respondents. On the other hand, the secondary data used in this research was obtained through library search and retrieval methods.

Population of the Study

The population of study covered 270 permanent staff of ExxonMobil Corporation, Eket. These respondents were drawn from selected departments (Finance department, Human resource management department, Safety department, Security department, Operational department). Permanent staff were chosen for this study because they have spent good number of years in the corporation and have reliable information about the working environment and its consequences on performance of employees.

Sample Size Determination

The researchers adopted ratio sampling technique to select 2/3 of the total population of the study. With a population of 270, $2/3$ of $270 = 180$; $0.6667 * 270 = 180$. In effect, the sample size of the study is 180 employees from the selected departments. Ratio sampling ($2/3$) was adopted because in every 3 persons sampled, 2 persons were likely to provide varying responses about organizational work environment. More so, with a shifting working culture, some of the employees might not be present at the office at time of visit for administration of questionnaire.

Model Specification and Variable Identification

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3) \dots \dots \dots 3.1$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_i \dots \dots 3.2$$

Y = Employee performance

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients

X_1 = Work condition

X_2 = Company culture

X_3 = Physical work condition

e_i = Error term

Analysis/Interpretation of Data

A total of one hundred and eighty (180) copies of questionnaire were administered to staff of ExxonMobil Corporation to respond on the organizational work environment and performance. However, 150 copies were properly filled and retrieved by the researchers and their assistants, implying that thirty (30) copies of the questionnaire lost in the process. Thus, 150(83.3%) copies of the administered questionnaires were retrieved and confirmed for analysis.

Table 1.0: Work Condition affect Employee Performance

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	x
Number of work hours and time of work (day or night) in ExxonMobil affects employee performance	40	58	29	14	9	180	2.70
	26.7%	38.7%	19.3%	9.3%	6.0%	100	
Terms of employment (contract / permanent staff, benefits and pay time) increases employee performance in ExxonMobil	105	41	4	-	-	180	3.67
	70.0%	27.3%	2.7%	-	-	100	
Work place safety measures in ExxonMobil enhance work performance	84	50	13	3	-	180	3.43
	56.0%	33.3%	8.7%	2.0%	-	100	

The health and lifestyle promoted by ExxonMobil enhances work performance	90	46	10	4	-	180	3.48
	60.0%	30.7%	6.6%	2.7%	-	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2021 Decision rule: mean value > 2.5 accepted, mean < 2.5 was rejected

Table 1.0 descriptively analyzed the effect of work condition on employee performance. From the result, 70.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that terms of employment (that is, contract / permanent staff, benefits and pay time) increases employee performance in ExxonMobil, Eket. 60.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that health and lifestyle promoted by ExxonMobil enhances work performance. More so, 56.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that work place safety measures in ExxonMobil enhance work performance. Lastly, 38.7% of the respondents agreed that the number of work hours and time of work (day or night) in ExxonMobil, Eket affects employee performance. Against this backdrop, 19.3% of the respondents disagreed that the number of work hours and time of work (day or night) in ExxonMobil, Eket affects employee performance. The precision through the mean value decision rule means that, a mean value > 2.5 was accepted while a mean < 2.5 was rejected.

The result shows that number of work hours and time of work (day or night) have a mean value of 2.70; terms of employment with a mean value of 3.67; work place safety measures has a mean value of 3.43; and the health and lifestyle promoted by ExxonMobil, Eket has a mean value of 3.48. From the descriptive questions, four (4) out of four (4) questions (items) had a mean value above 2.5, implying none of the items had a mean value less than 2.5. Since the mean are all above 2.5, we concluded that work condition in ExxonMobil, Eket significantly affect employee performance.

Table 1.1: Work Culture in Exxon Mobil, Eket and Employee Performance

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	x
Work locations (indoors and outdoors) in ExxonMobil, Eket affect employee performance	78	60	9	3	-	180	3.42
	52.0%	40.0%	9.0%	2.0%	-	100	
The employee code of conduct that guides employee behavior in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance	81	53	12	4	-	180	3.40
	54.0%	35.3%	8.0%	2.7%	-	100	
Collaborations, team works and positive feedbacks in ExxonMobil, Eket work environment increases employee performance	103	42	4	1	-	180	3.64
	68.7%	28.0%	2.7%	0.6%	-	100	

The company values and goals of ExxonMobil, Eket enhance employee performances	40	40	31	35	4	180	2.51
	26.7%	26.7%	20.6%	23.3%	2.7%	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2021 Decision rule: mean value > 2.5 accepted, mean < 2.5 was rejected

As recorded in Table 1.1 above, large percentage of the respondents (68.7%) strongly agreed that collaborations, team work, and positive feedbacks in Exxon Mobil, Eket increase employee performance. This is followed by 54.0% of the respondents who strongly agreed the employee code of conduct in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance. More so, 53.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that work locations (indoors and outdoors) in ExxonMobil, Eket affect employee performance, while 26.7% of the respondents agreed that the company’s values and goals enhance employee performance. However, 23.3% (35) of the respondents strongly disagreed that the company’s values and goals of ExxonMobil, Eket enhance employee performance.

The mean value of the items showed that work locations (indoors and outdoors) have a mean value of 3.42; the employee code of conduct that guides employee behavior has a mean value of 3.40; collaborations, team works, and positive feedbacks have a mean value of 3.64; and the company’s values and goals of Exxon Mobil, Eket has a mean value of 2.51. From the result, four (4) out of four (4) items had a mean value greater than 2.5, and none of the objective questions had a mean value less than 2.5. Based on the decision rule that a mean value > 2.5 is accepted while a mean < 2.5 is rejected, we concluded that, work culture in ExxonMobil, Eket has a significant effect on employee performance.

Table 1.2: Physical environment ExxonMobil, Eket and Employee Performance

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	\bar{x}
The size of work space in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance	76 50.7%	57 38.0%	15 10.0%	- -	2 1.3%	180 100	3.36
The design of work space in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance	22 14.7%	47 31.3%	42 28.0%	30 20%	8 5.3%	180 100	2.28
The work space furniture in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance	56 37.3%	77 51.3%	13 8.7%	4 2.7%	- -	180 100	3.23
The working equipment in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance	81 54.0%	45 30.0%	18 12.0%	6 4.0%	- -	180 100	3.34
Special facilities such as onsite gym and relaxing space in ExxonMobil, Eket increases employee performance	97 64.7%	51 54.0%	2 1.3%	- -	- -	180 100	3.63

Source: Field Survey, 2021 Decision rule: mean value > 2.5 accepted, mean < 2.5 was rejected

The analysis of table 1.2 above revealed that 64.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that special facilities such as onsite gym and relaxing space in ExxonMobil, Eket increase employee performance; 54.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that work equipment in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance; 50.7% of the respondents agreed that size of work space in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance. In addition, 51.3% of the respondents agreed that work space furniture in ExxonMobil, Eket enhances employee performance; and 31.3% of the respondents agreed that design of work space in Exxon Mobil, Eket enhances employee performance. However, only 28.0% of the respondents disagreed that design of work space in Exxon Mobil, Eket enhances employee performance. Judging from the result, a mean value > 2.5 is accepted while a mean < 2.5 is rejected. The size of work space has a mean value of 3.23; the design of work space has a mean value of 2.28; the work space furniture has a mean value of 3.25; the working equipment space has a mean value of 3.34; and Special facilities such as onsite gym and relaxing space in ExxonMobil Eket has a mean value of 3.63. From the result, five (5) out of four (4) items had a mean value greater than 2.5, and one (1) of the research statements had a mean value less than 2.5. With this, we concluded that 80% of the respondents strongly agreed that physical environment ExxonMobil, Eket significantly affect employee performance.

Test of Hypotheses

From the stated hypotheses and model specified for this research, the result of the multiple linear regression model is shown as follows:

Table 1.3: Multiple linear regression analysis result on effect of work environment (condition, culture, physical) on employee performance

Variable	Parameters	Coefficient	Std error	Tcal – value
Constant	β_0	-0.115	0.199	-0.576
Work condition (X_1)	β_1	0.515	0.087	5.995***
Work culture (X_2)	β_2	0.374	0.076	4.915***
Physical environment (X_3)	β_3	0.133	0.061	2.190**
R-Square (R^2)		0.692		
Adjusted R – Square (R^{-2})		0.685		
F – Statistics		109.221		
F – Probability		0.000		

*** (1%), ** (5%), and * (10%) denotes significance of coefficient at level

t-tab value = 1.976 df = 146 Dependent Variable: employee performance

Predictors: (Constant), physical environment, work culture, work condition

Source: Field Survey, 2021 (SPSS Version 20 computation)

Table 1.3 above shows the result of multiple linear regression analysis on the effect of work environment (condition, culture, physical) on employee performance in ExxonMobil. From the result, the t-calculated value of work condition, work culture and physical environment were 5.995, 4.915 and 2.190 which are greater than t-tabulated value of 1.976, hence, work condition, work culture and physical environment in ExxonMobil have significant effect on employee performance.

The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.692, which implies that 69.2% changes in the dependent variable was explained by changes in the independent variable, while 30.8% was unexplained by the stochastic terms in the model. Thus, the independent variable (work condition, work culture and physical environment) can only explain 69.2 percent of changes on employee performance in Exxon Mobil, Eket, leaving 30.8% unexplained. The R^2 adjusted was 68.5% indicating a goodness of fit of the regression model adopted in this study which is statistically significant at 5% probability level. More so, the f-statistical (calculated) value of 109.221 which is greater than 1.976 t-table value; and f-probability value of 0.000 observed to be less than 0.05 (95% of freedom), indicate that estimated regression model adopted in this study is statistically significant at 5% level. Since the t-calculated value is greater than t-tabulated value in absolute terms, the researcher rejected the null hypotheses in favour of alternative hypothesis; hence, work condition, work culture and physical environment in ExxonMobil have significant effect on employee performance.

Decision rule for hypothesis 1

Table 1.4: H_0 : Work condition in Exxon Mobil has no significant effect on employee performance.

Variable	Coefficient	t-calculated value	Prob.
Work condition	0.763	5.995	0.000
T- tabulated: 1.976			

Source: Computed from Table 1.3

From the result, work condition (X_1) has a statistical value of 5.996 with a probability value of 0.000 at 5% level of significance which is greater than 1.976 t-table value. Since the t-cal value is greater than t-tab value in absolute terms so, we reject null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis, thus, work condition in Exxon Mobil has significant effect on employee performance.

Decision rule for hypothesis 2

Table 1.5: H₀: Work culture in Exxon Mobil has no significant effect on employee performance.

Variable	Coefficient	t-calculated value	Prob.
Work culture	0.374	4.915	0.000

T- tabulated: 1.976

Source: Computed from Table 1.3

From the result, work culture (X_2) has a statistical value of 4.915 with a probability value of 0.000 at 5% level of significance, which is greater than 1.976 t-table value. Since the t-cal value is greater than t-tab value in absolute terms, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of alternative hypothesis, thus, work culture in ExxonMobil has significant effect on employee performance.

Decision rule for hypothesis 3

Table 1.6: H₀: Physical work environment in Exxon Mobil has no significant effect on employee performance.

Variable	Coefficient	t-calculated value	Prob.
Physical work environment	0.133	2.190	0.030

T- tabulated: 1.976

Source: Computed from Table 1.3

From the result, physical work environment (X_3) has a statistical value of 2.190 with a probability value of 0.030 at 5% level of significance, which is greater than 1.976 t-table value. Since the t-cal value is greater than t-tab value in absolute terms, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of alternative hypothesis. This also shows that physical work environment in ExxonMobil has significant effect on employee performance.

Summary / Conclusion

The study examined how organizational work environment in ExxonMobil, Eket affects employee performance. In specific terms, the work condition, work culture and physical work environment on employee performance were tested. The data were sourced through administration of questionnaire, and results from the tested hypotheses revealed that work condition, work culture, and physical environment in Exxon Mobil have significant effects on employee performance. This result agrees

with the findings of researchers like Athirah-Saidi, Michael, Sumilan, Lim, Jonathan, Hamidi and Ahmad (2019); Ollukkaran and Gunaseelan (2012); Awan and Tahir (2015), whose researches also centered on the same subject-matter.

Since money is not a sufficient motivator in encouraging the workplace performance required in today's competitive business environment, work environment plays a vital role in motivating employees to perform their assigned jobs. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the organization to provide friendly working environment which will influence employees to work comfortably and perform their job.

Recommendation

Based on the result of this research, the following are recommendations for future implementation:

1. Exxon Mobil Corporation, Eket must maintain a better environment in order to enhance employee productivity as employee performance and workplace environment have direct and positive relationship.
2. There is need for periodic meetings with employees to air their grievances to management to serve as a motivating factor to the employees.
3. Management should try as much as possible to build a work environment that attracts, retain and motivate its employees so as to help them work comfortably and increase organization productivity.
4. Employers should have in place a good working condition for their employees in order to boost their morale and make them more efficient. An example is making their benefit programs to suit employees.

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